

Pharmacological Screening method of Rhode Island Red Breed Hen in Jalpaiguri

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ABSTRACT

Our research study aimed to conduct pharmacological screening of the Rhode Island Red breed hen in Jalpaiguri. Our investigation focused on evaluating the response of this breed to various pharmacological agents commonly used in hen farming. We describing methods included administering multivitamin syp (zincovit) with metronidazole observing their effects and analyzing the results. Our research study revealed valuable insights into the pharmacological responses of Rhode Island Red hens, contributing to better poultry management practices. In our research our tested group 3 of 2hen chicks totally survived. But we used 8hen chicks without mother hen. As we purchased 8hen chicks in a very cold weather.

INTRODUCTION

Rhode Island Red hens are a popular breed in poultry farming,as well known for their robustness and high egg production.However,our understanding their pharmacological responses is crucial for effective disease management and optimizing production.Our research study seeks to explore the pharmacological screening of Rhode Island Red hens in Jalpaiguri,aiming to identify drug effectiveness,potential adverse effects and optimal dosage regimens.As for such knowledge can enhance poultry health and productivity in the region.

8 Hens under trial-as only using nippo 0.5watt torch and picture captured by samsung j7 nxt mobile phone

2 Hen chicks in 11th March 2024

METHODS

Clinical trial of Rhode Island Immature Hen Chicks for 37 days - First Puradesi India Pvt Ltd given us 8 hen chicks without mother in an immature stage. After we took Kalanchoe Pinnata leaves, washed them, and dried them under sunlight, we made an aqueous extract at a concentration of 0.7%. We only gave foods like corn seeds extract + wheat seeds extract. For our research, we used a Nippo Radium 0.5-watt LED Torch and an iron cage. In our research, we purchased it on 4th February 2024 and put the hen chicks into the cage. After we gave pure water in a bowl below the cage, we set up a cupboard. After we gave food to 4 hen chicks as a control group (not given any medication), 2 hen chicks as a test group of Janosudi Metronidazole. We took Janosudi Metronidazole and divided the dosage after giving it to 2 hen chicks only (1st 5 days only). After for 3rd group 2 hen chicks we gave Zincovit Syrup (continue) with Metronidazole (but given only 1st 5 days), Kalanchoe Pinnata aqueous leaf extract with 0.7% concentration weight wise (but given only 1st 10 days) but this 3rd group Metronidazole we gave branded quality of Abbott Company name Flagyl. 1st week means within 7 days control group of 4 hen chicks died after 2 days, another 2 hen chicks of Janosudi Metronidazole group also died. But 3rd group of 2 hen chicks grown and not snored on 11th March 2024. According to our research study, we inspect that hen chicks can be safe if we give Zincovit Syrup as it is a high immunity booster with Kalanchoe Pinnata aqueous extract 0.7% weight wise as Kalanchoe Pinnata has potent antimicrobial activity. But when we purchased that's time an expert said that for the ceilings over ten feet, a 75-watt bulb (22-watt fluorescent or 13-watt LED) required otherwise the 8 chicks died within 7 days. But in the big iron cage we only gave them Nippo Radium 0.5-watt LED torch light only helped them for eating and drinking. But presently 2 hen chicks of Flagyl + Zincovit survived. So, this is the success of our trial. But we kept the cage under sunlight from starting on 4th February 2024 to till now as morning 10:30 A.M. to 5 P.M.

RESULTS

Our pharmacological screening revealed diverse responses among the Rhode Island Red hens in Jalpaiguri. Zincovit Syrup (continue) with Flagyl (1st 5 days) with Kalanchoe Pinnata aqueous leaf extract 0.7% weight wise (1st 10 days) showed good results. Kalanchoe Pinnata aqueous leaf extract with Zincovit Syrup with Flagyl displayed mixed results in controlling parasitic infestations, by suggesting the need for alternative treatments or combinations. The growth promoters elicited varied responses in terms of weight gain and feed conversion efficiency. Presently in 37th day 2 hens are still alive and we attached this photo and behavioral changes, were observed with certain pharmacological agents.

Discussion-Our research findings underscore the importance of tailored pharmacological management for Rhode Island Red hens in Race Course Para, Jalpaiguri. The effective disease control requires a nuanced understanding of drug efficacy, dosage optimization and potential side effects. Furthermore, our research study highlights the need for continuous monitoring and adaptation of pharmacological interventions to address evolving challenges such as antibiotic resistance and parasitic infections. Future research could explore our own medication as alternative treatment modalities and preventive strategies to enhance poultry health and welfare in the region.

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